

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** **TARAQQIYOT** va

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Elektron nashr. 882 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

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THE USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROVISION OF UTILITIES TO THE POPULATION

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Abstract: The given article presents proposals for the use of digital technologies in improving the quality of public services and enhancing the quality of life of the population.

Key words: smart home, smart city, smart company, safe city, smart meter.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada aholi turmush darajasi va sifatini yaxshilash hamda kommunal xizmatlar sifatini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish bo'yicha takliflar ko'rsatib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: aqlli uy, aqlli shahar, aqlli shirkat, xavfsiz shahar, aqlli hisoblagich.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены предложения по использованию цифровых технологий в повышении качества коммунальных услуг и повышении качества жизни населения.

Ключевые слова: умный дом, умный город, умная компания, безопасный город, умный счётчик.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the role of the field of utilities in improving the standard of living and quality of the population of our country is very large. This situation requires special attention to the organization and efficiency of the activities of the utility sector [7]. In order to develop this area, a number of legal and regulatory documents in our country are included, in particular, the housing, urban planning codes, laws "on the protection of consumer rights", "on rent", "on mortgages", "on electricity", "on the use of water and water", "on waste". Improving the efficiency of the system of utilities for the population using these laws effectively ensures the rise of the

socio-economic sphere. Therefore, reforms in the field of the utility system are an integral component of the socio-economic changes taking place in our country.

In the countries of the world, the conditions of transition to the digital economy and the sphere of Public Utilities are considered as one of the main factors in the rise in the standard of living of the population [2]. In connection with the rapid increase in the global population, the expansion of the housing stock, on the one hand, leads to an increase in the level of the real need of consumers for utilities, on the other hand, leads to an increase in the level of demand for the quality of services consumed and, therefore, requires an approach to the volume of utilities. This makes it necessary to increase the efficiency of the public utility system and improve the processes of digitization in accordance with existing changes.

REVIEW OF THEMATIC LITERATURE

Of the many foreign scientists who have carried out scientific research on improving the system of Housing and communal services in the regions, E. Ostrom, S.Nahrath, P.Chemetov, R.Baudoui, D.Paris, F.O.Seys, M.P. Johnson, P.Osborn, M.S.Jensen, M.Leitch, P.Smets, P. Van Lindert, S.Ganapati, S.Wheeler, J.Plammer, S.Of particular importance is the scientific work of scientists such as Heimans.

Some aspects of the system of management of Housing and communal services are also studied in the research of scientists of our country. Specifically: M.Q.Ziyaev, R.I.Nurimbetov, V.U.Khabanov, I.X.Davletov, O.Sh. Mamanazarov, T.A.Hasanov, R.R.Platova, D.Ya.Butunov, CA.E.Rahimov A.S. In the research of scientists of our country, such as Sultanov, issues of managing the housing stock and improving the quality of Housing and communal services are reflected.

A. on issues of development of the utility sector. V.Chechulin, S.I.Shelonaev, T.V.Smetanina” smart city”: experiments and prosperity in the management of the Russian state” discussed the general principles and models of “smart” management and studied the existing foreign experience. An analysis of the regulatory framework and programs for the implementation of “smart city” projects has been given by the regions of the Russian Federation. The article also proposes a classification of programs of horizontal and vertical models. The specifics of managing the implementation of “smart city” projects by territorial entities are also covered [1].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the research process carried out to write our scientific article, methods of scientific observation, abstract-logical thinking, comparative and systematic analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic approach, induction and deduction were used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Currently, the ongoing digitization process is creating fundamental changes in the global economy due to the savings in costs associated with the collection, processing, transmission and distribution of information. But the process of digital transformation should not be considered a simple introduction of Information Technology [3].

It should be understood that most methods about the utility transformation process are a whole existing model of a particular utility that involves investing in utility technologies, that is, a set of changes such as direct structure, development strategy, customer work, product promotion and service methods, and even service culture.

Digitization reduces the cost and value of payments and becomes a new source of income. Remuneration for services provided in an online environment will be significantly less than in the traditional economy (especially because of the reduction in the cost of services related to realism), while public and commercial services will become popular for all. In addition, in the digital world, goods and services can quickly find their buyer in the global market and become more affordable than anywhere in the world. The services provided will be able to be processed in the short term in accordance with the habits of consumers. The digital economy has become a reality in retail, transport, telecommunications, insurance and banking. Digital transformation on a Buggingi day applies to almost any field of activity. The initial stage of the introduction of “Smart City” Innovation Technologies continues in our country [3].

In the cities of our country, preliminary testing projects on “safe city”, “smart meters”, “smart transport”, “directions of smart medicine” are planned and implemented. Its main goal is to implement measures aimed at creating modern engineering and communication infrastructures of cities through the introduction of smart city “ technologies. In this concept, the main directions and stages of the introduction of “smart city” innovation technologies were expressed, measures were developed to increase them to practice.

The main goal of "smart city" technologies is to improve the quality of living of people, to provide them with comfort, to effectively use the available resources. The "smart home" serves to save resources as well as improve the quality of life of people by introducing various "smart" elements based on the needs of the host. That being said, digital transformation opens up many possibilities. First, the proceeds grow. This is due to the launch of new lines of business, products and services. For example, in the field of Telecommunications, it can be digital services for music and video streaming (streaming online broadcasting) or cloud platforms for smart home [3].

Forms of innovation of the utility system "universal housing and communal services", "smart homes" will lead to the development and improvement of the efficiency of the system of digitization of municipal accounting. Today, when creating a "smart home" system, such indicators as air temperature, humidity level, atmospheric pressure and illumination level, the level of ensuring home security control, LF digitization is widely used.

The implementation of the "Universal housing utility" requires the use of informative devices of the types of innovation utilities ("smart meters", "smart home", "safe house", "smart company"). In turn, the organization of the process of working together these devices is an urgent issue. In addition, a team of employees with special knowledge and skills is required to control the process of processing devices. The process of controlling the work of the worker-employee carries additional responsibility for the subjects of management. This naturally requires additional material, financial and human resources.

In our opinion, in order to eliminate problems in the provision of utilities, a remote device system is needed, which, in a completely autonomous way, without human intervention, provides air parameters in the specified area, in particular:

- determination of air temperature and relative humidity, atmospheric pressure and illumination;
- should be able to automatically, independently start additional devices based on indicators, as well as ensure disconnection from the power source.

It seems to us that when solving these issues, it is advisable to use the "Benux" system. Because, "Benux" is a multifunctional and protocol system that is also widely used in control and other areas for its convenience (Figure 1).

Figure 1: System "Universal housing and communal services"[4]

For example, by being away from home or office, it is possible to receive information about sensors on a mobile phone by e-mail, ICQ or SMS. In addition, in a simple browser, the video camera provides information about the photocells, temperature graph, state of various sensors and controls electrical devices. Remote

control of systems is carried out on the basis of the Internet, ICQ or SMS message. A sensor status detection system is used for visual control and control [6].

The next step in designing smart homes is considered door sensors, which can be used for many purposes. The principle of the door sensor is simple, it consists of two parts, and when they are separated, they send a signal. Some of them also indicate the temperature that you can use to optimize heating. To give you some ideas on door sensors: turn on the lights when you enter the House installed on the door, listen to music on the radio system, turn on the heating if you do not have a thermostat with geofencing, send a signal if you are not at home when the door opens, report open windows when the rain installed on the windows

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In our opinion, the use of digital technologies in the utility system in improving the efficiency of utilities serves, first of all, to increase the quality of utilities and reduce their cost [2]:

- secondly, by putting into practice the processes of digitalization of utility enterprises, it is possible to save resources and reduce costs;
- third, corruption cases can be avoided;
- fourth, we can achieve the effective organization of the activities of the utility system.

We think that the above-recognized cases serve to improve the efficiency of the communal system on the one hand, and the quality and level of living of the population on the other.

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Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2024. № 4

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

